

IMI2 Project 802750 - FAIRplus
FAIRification of IMI and EFPIA data

WP2 – Development of FAIRification process for selected data sources and implementation

D2.6 FAIR Data Set Maturity model

Lead contributor	Ibrahim Emam (11 - Imperial College)
	i.emam@imperial.ac.uk
Other contributors	Philippe Rocca-Serra (03 - UOXF)
	Susanna-Assunta Sansone (03 - UOXF)
	Laura Portell-Silva (08 - BSC)
	Yojana Gadiya (02 - Fraunhofer ITMP)
	Danielle Welter (07 - University of Luxembourg)
	Nick Juty (04 - The University of Manchester)
	Tooba Abbassi-Daloi (05 - Maastricht University)

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1. Executive Summary

The FAIR Dataset Maturity (DSM) model¹ is intended as a comprehensive reference model for state-of-FAIRness improvement in research datasets. Based on the FAIR guiding principles, the DSM model defines and classifies requirements that constitute an incremental path towards improving FAIRness level for a given research dataset. The FAIR DSM has also been applied to the FAIR Cookbook recipes, and used it to assess the FAIRified datasets.

Motivations and Objectives

The motivation that drove the development of the FAIR-DSM model was fueled by the needs of both data consumers and data producers to find a common reference model to assess the state of FAIRness of research data. Existing models focus on the development of indicators as a means to assess the fulfilment of each FAIR principle, while the concept of ‘FAIR maturity’ of the data object as a whole is often left underdeveloped. In the case of the RDA² indicators, the concept of maturity was associated with each indicator. This allows assessing the level of maturity towards achieving each indicator. This however, does not naturally lend itself to understanding the overall maturity of the data object; Fulfilling different subsets of indicators, which reflect different FAIR requirements, produces equivalent maturity scores, making it even harder to provide a meaning to such scores.

Furthermore, due to the absence of a FAIR reference model, the decisions taken to FAIRify data were often subject to the biases of the individual driving the process. This often can lead to unjustified investments in certain aspects of the FAIRification process that require a lot of effort but have very little impact on the use case for the FAIRified data. For example, standardising and enriching the description of metadata according to community standards is one of the elements of the FAIR principles. However, unless the standardisation of data is accompanied by similar investments into hosting and providing accessibility for this well described and structured metadata, the standardisation step becomes much less impactful. Similarly, investing into the interoperability of data by transforming them into semantically-annotated representations, using community-defined terminologies is not that valuable if data is only going to be used within a closed project collaboration, where perhaps other processes, such as lighter-touch data harmonisation across the project’s datasets, would provide better value at lower costs.

¹ <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/recipes/maturity.html>

² <https://zenodo.org/record/3909563>

Motivated by solving the aforementioned challenges, the FAIR-DSM was developed with two objectives in mind: (i) provide an unambiguous assessment approach that focuses on the overall state-of-FAIRness of datasets, in light of their expected ‘usability’; and (ii) provide a reference maturity model that defines different levels of FAIR data, where each level reflects a different state-of-FAIRness, providing a meaningful target for implementing a FAIRification process and a set of guidelines that will enable a data usability goal that each target level is associated with.

2. Methods

FAIR Principle	Classification	RDA ID	RDA Indicator	Related FAIR principles	Description	FAIR+FAIR
A1	Content	RDA-A1-01M	Metadata contains information to enable the user to get access to the data	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol.	access information	FsF-A1-01M: Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.
F1	Content	RDA-F1-02M	Metadata is identified by a globally unique identifier	F1 (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier.	GUI for metadata object	N/A
F1	Content	RDA-F1-02D	Data is identified by a globally unique identifier	F1 (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier.	GUI for data object	FsF-F1-02D: Data is assigned a globally unique identifier
F2	Content	RDA-F2-01M	Rich metadata is provided to allow discovery	F2: Data are described with rich metadata.	metadata descriptive elements to enable search capability	FsF-F2-01M: Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.
F3	Content	RDA-F3-01M	Metadata includes the identifier for the data	F3: Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe.	metadata includes Data GUI	FsF-F3-01M: Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.
I2	Content	RDA-I2-01M	Metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies	I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles.	Use of defined data elements (e.g. ISO 11179 DEs)	FsF-I2-01M: Metadata uses semantic resources
I2	Content	RDA-I2-01D	Data uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies	I2: (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles.	Use of controlled vocabularies / ontologies	N/A
I3	Content	RDA-I3-01M	Metadata includes references to other metadata	I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	metadata-to-metadata links	FsF-I3-01M: Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities
I3	Content	RDA-I3-01D	Data includes references to other data	I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	data-to-data links	FsF-I3-01M: Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities
I3	Content	RDA-I3-02M	Metadata includes references to other data	I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	metadata-to-data links	FsF-I3-01M: Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities
I3	Content	RDA-I3-02D	Data includes qualified references to other data	I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	data-to-data links (annotated)	FsF-I3-01M: Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities
I3	Content	RDA-I3-03M	Metadata includes qualified references to other metadata	I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	metadata-to-metadata links (annotated)	FsF-I3-01M: Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities
I3	Content	RDA-I3-04M	Metadata include qualified references to other data	I3: (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	metadata-to-data links (annotated)	FsF-I3-01M: Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities
R1	Content	RDA-R1-01M	Plurality of accurate and relevant attributes are provided to allow reuse	R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.	Metadata describes data content	FsF-R1-01M: Metadata specifies the content of the data.
R1.1	Content	RDA-R1.1-01M	Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data can be reused	R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence.	metadata includes locally defined data usage licence	FsF-R1.1-01M: Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.
R1.1	Content	RDA-R1.1-02M	Metadata refers to a standard reuse licence	R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence.	metadata includes standard data usage licence	FsF-R1.1-01M: Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.
R1.2	Content	RDA-R1.2-01M	Metadata includes provenance information according to community-specific standards	R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance.	Provenance information represented in community standard	FsF-R1.2-01M: Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.
R1.2	Content	RDA-R1.2-02M	Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language	R1.2: (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance.	Provenance information represented in cross-domain format	FsF-R1.2-01M: Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.
I1	Format and representation	RDA-I1-01D	Data uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	data format (standardized format)	N/A
I1	Format and representation	RDA-I1-02D	Data uses machine-understandable knowledge representation	I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	data representation (Machine-readable) - no community standard	N/A
I1	Format and representation	RDA-I1-02M	Metadata uses machine-understandable knowledge representation	I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	metadata representation (Machine-readable)	FsF-I1-01M: Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.
I1	Format and representation	RDA-I1-01M	Metadata uses knowledge representation expressed in standardised format	I1: (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	metadata format (use contr. vocab)	FsF-I1-01M: Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.
R1.1	Format and representation	RDA-R1.1-03M	Metadata refers to a machine-understandable reuse licence	R1.1: (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage licence.	metadata representation of licence info in machine readable format	FsF-R1.1-01M: Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.
R1.3	Format and representation	RDA-R1.3-01M	Metadata complies with a community standard	R1.3: (Meta)data meet domainrelevant community standards.	metadata representation (standard metadata model)	FsF-R1.3-01M: Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.
R1.3	Format and representation	RDA-R1.3-02M	Metadata is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard	R1.3: (Meta)data meet domainrelevant community standards.	metadata representation (standard metadata model) & format (machine readable)	FsF-R1.3-01M: Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.
R1.3	Format and representation	RDA-R1.3-01D	Data complies with a community standard	R1.3: (Meta)data meet domainrelevant community standards.	data representation (standard data model)	FsF-R1.3-02D: Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.
R1.3	Format and representation	RDA-R1.3-02D	Data is expressed in compliance with a machine-understandable community standard	R1.3: (Meta)data meet domainrelevant community standards.	data representation (standard data model) & format (machine readable)	FsF-R1.3-02D: Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.
A1	Hosting environment	RDA-A1-02M	Metadata can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol.	Retrieval Capability (metadata) (manual) (links)	FsF-A1-02M: Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
A1	Hosting environment	RDA-A1-02D	Data can be accessed manually (i.e. with human intervention)	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol.	Retrieval Capability (data) (manual) (links)	FsF-A1-02M: Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
A1	Hosting environment	RDA-A1-03M	Metadata identifier resolves to a metadata record	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol.	Retrieval Capability (metadata) via service	FsF-A1-02M: Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
A1	Hosting environment	RDA-A1-03D	Data identifier resolves to a digital object	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol.	Retrieval Capability (data retrievable) via service	FsF-A1-02M: Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
A1	Hosting environment	RDA-A1-04M	Metadata is accessed through standardised protocol	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol.	Retrieval Capability (metadata) (standard protocol) HTTP & FTP	FsF-A1-02M: Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
A1	Hosting environment	RDA-A1-04D	Data is accessible through standardised protocol	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol.	Retrieval Capability (data) (standard protocol) HTTP & FTP	FsF-A1-03D: Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
A1	Hosting environment	RDA-A1-05D	Data can be accessed automatically (i.e. by a computer program)	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communication protocol.	Retrieval Capability (API)	FsF-A1-03D: Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
A1.1	Hosting environment	RDA-A1.1-01M	Metadata is accessible through a free access protocol	A1.1: The protocol is open, free and universally implementable	Retrieval Capability (metadata) (open protocol) HTTP & FTP	FsF-A1-03D: Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
A1.1	Hosting environment	RDA-A1.1-01D	Data is accessible through a free access protocol	A1.1: The protocol is open, free and universally implementable	Retrieval Capability (data) (open protocol) HTTP & FTP	FsF-A1-03D: Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
A1.2	Hosting environment	RDA-A1.2-01D	Data is accessible through an access protocol that supports authentication and authorisation	A1.2: The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation where necessary	Retrieval Capability (data) (auth impl)	FsF-A1-03D: Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
A2	Hosting environment	RDA-A2-01M	Metadata is guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available	A2: Metadata should be accessible even when the data is no longer available.	Archiving Capability (metadata)	FsF-A1-03D: Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
F1	Hosting environment	RDA-F1-01M	Metadata is identified by a persistent identifier	F1 (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier.	Metadata object persisted (saved) in a resource with PID	N/A
F1	Hosting environment	RDA-F1-01D	Data is identified by a persistent identifier	F1 (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and eternally persistent identifier.	Data object persisted (saved) in a resource with PID	FsF-F1-01D: Data is assigned a persistent identifier
F4	Hosting environment	RDA-F4-01M	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed	F4: (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource.	Search Capability (Metadata record, stored and indexed)	FsF-F4-01M: Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by humans

Figure 1. Classification of RDA & FAIRsFAIR indicators into three classes of FAIR requirements.

Classification of Existing Indicators

The process of developing the FAIR-DSM model began with an exercise to reclassify and align³ the already existing indicators from the RDA⁴ FAIR Data Maturity model and

³https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/18T83wgc_Zl-z-BcQULLmi2sUoMg9lYnc7j_ZhyCBSzA/edit#gid=64919941

⁴<https://zenodo.org/record/3909563>

the FAIRsFAIR⁵ model. The objective of this exercise was to identify the different underlying intent of each indicator / FAIR principle with respect to the FAIR data object to establish its FAIR state. This exercise led to the identification of three common themes across the four FAIR principles. The first group included all indicators that referred to the representation of data and metadata in different standard models and formats ('representation and format'). The second group was a subset of indicators that required the 'inclusion' of certain elements in the data or metadata objects subject to FAIRification ('content and context'). The third group included indicators that described different capabilities that ought to be provided by the hosting environments to enable and support the expected use of FAIRness of the data and metadata objects ('hosting environment').

Development of the FAIR DSM Indicators

Based on these three identified common themes of FAIR requirements we consolidated the list of indicators from both the RDA and the FAIRsFAIR groups and created an interim list of indicators and classified them into three categories, which we then used to develop the early versions of the FAIR DSM five levels maturity model. We used the three identified categories as three dimensions to express an increasing path of maturity for a dataset's FAIRness level. This was achieved by distributing the existing indicators onto a grid view as seen in Figure 2⁶. The y-axis represents each category of indicators, while the x-axis represents the different maturity levels, each including indicators from the three categories.

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6461229>

⁶ https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/18T83wgc_Zj-z-BcQULLmi2sUoMg9lYnc7j_ZhyCBSzA/view#gid=1986480902

Categories	Level 0	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	Level 4	Level 5
[R] Representation & Format	DSM-0-R1Contextual Metadata is NOT formally represented in any form	DSM-1-R0Dataset Metadata is formally represented in the form of an identifiable Dataset Descriptor	DSM-2-R1Contextual Metadata is formally represented and reported in the form of a locally defined Domain Model	DSM-3-R1Contextual Metadata is formally represented and modeled according to a community or domain-specific standard	DSM-4-R1Contextual Metadata is formally represented by a set of semantically defined Common Data Elements	DSM-5-R1Data content and context is defined and managed by Master Data Management
	DSM-0-R2No representation of Data purposed for sharing and re-use is available	DSM-1-R1Contextual Metadata is represented at summary level and reported in the Dataset Descriptor	DSM-2-R2Dataset(s) are standardised to a locally defined Dataset Model suitable for data sharing and re-use	DSM-3-R2Dataset(s) are standardised to relevant Domain or Community Standard Dataset Model(s) suitable for data sharing and re-use	DSM-4-R2Dataset(s) are standardised to a defined Semantic Data Model and represented using Linked Data Representations suitable for data sharing and re-use	DSM-5-R2Dataset(s) intended for sharing and re-use are granularly standardised and managed at the Data Element Level (e.g. ISO 11179 MDR standard)
	DSM-0-R3Metadata is available but NOT formally represented in a structured Dataset Descriptor	DSM-1-R2Data intended for sharing and reuse have a purposely defined representation as Datasets	DSM-2-R3Dataset Descriptor(s) adopt a Metadata Schema representation that describes the locally defined Dataset Model including its structural metadata (i.e. Field-level and Value-level metadata)	DSM-3-R3Dataset Descriptor(s) use community-defined or domain-specific metadata standard	DSM-4-R3A Semantic Data Model (Metadata) used for data harmonisation across Datasets is formally defined and represented using Linked Data Representations	DSM-5-R3Common Data Elements and their value sets are defined and registered in a managed Metadata Registry
	DSM-0-R4Metadata is NOT available in a Machine Readable Format	DSM-1-R3A representation of the Dataset Descriptor conforming to a relevant General Purpose Metadata Schema is available	DSM-2-R4A formal documentation of the locally defined Domain Model is available in a Human Readable Format	DSM-3-R4A formal documentation of the adopted Standard Dataset Model is available in a Machine Readable Format	DSM-4-R4A Semantic Data Model (Metadata) describing the data is represented in a Machine Readable and Machine Interpretable format	DSM-5-R4[Metadata Formatting requirements]
	DSM-0-R5Dataset(s) are NOT available in a Machine Readable Format	DSM-1-R4Dataset Descriptor is available in Machine Readable Format	DSM-2-R5Dataset(s) available in Machine Readable Format	DSM-3-R5Dataset(s) available in non-proprietary Machine Readable Format as prescribed by a standard Dataset Model	DSM-4-R5Dataset(s) are available in a Machine Readable and Machine Interpretable format	DSM-5-R5[Dataset Formatting requirements]
	DSM-1-R5Dataset(s) available in Machine Readable Format			DSM-4-R6If applicable, license information and/or permitted use and accessibility to parts of the dataset is formally represented and encoded in a Machine Readable Format		
[C] Content & Context	DSM-0-C0Dataset(s) are NOT identifiable via Unique Identifiers	DSM-1-C0Each Dataset purposed for sharing and re-use is assigned a unique identifier	DSM-2-C1The locally defined Domain Model contains concepts that describes the overall project/study design, the relationships between the Datasets, the key entities reported within the Datasets and the relationships between them.	DSM-3-C1Where applicable, study-level / experimental metadata is reported in compliance with relevant Minimum Information Reporting Guidelines	DSM-4-C1A Semantic Data Model includes study design Data Elements and the relationships between them	DSM-5-C1WHAT's included in the MASTER Data Consolidation Model
	DSM-0-C1Metadata does NOT contain context-related information required to interpret the data	DSM-1-C1Dataset Descriptor(s) includes Descriptive Study/Project-Level summary information	DSM-2-C2Where applicable, data is structured in the Dataset according to the Tidy Data Principles	DSM-3-C2Where applicable, Dataset(s) definition and content are reported in compliance with relevant community-defined Data Reporting Guidelines	DSM-4-C2Dataset(s) content is harmonised against a designed-for-purpose Semantic Data Model	DSM-5-C2
	DSM-0-C2Dataset Descriptor does NOT include a reference to the Dataset it describes	DSM-1-C2Dataset Descriptor(s) includes Identifying & Descriptive Dataset-Level metadata	DSM-2-C3Dataset(s) include Reference Fields that enable joining related datasets	DSM-3-C3Where applicable, Dataset Field Names use standard controlled terms as recommended by the adopted Standard	DSM-4-C3Key Dataset Fields are mapped to Common Data Elements as defined by the Semantic Data Model	DSM-5-C3Dataset Fields are linked and harmonised against enterprise managed Metadata Elements (e.g. MDR registered Data Elements)
		DSM-1-C3Dataset Descriptor(s) contains access information for the Dataset	DSM-2-C4Where applicable, Dataset Field Values are standardized against a locally defined Data Dictionary within and across related Datasets	DSM-3-C4Where applicable, Dataset Field Values are standardized against domain-specific Controlled Terminologies and/or Ontology Terms	DSM-4-C4Values for key Domain Entities reported in the Dataset(s) are standardised and assigned unique Standard Identifiers	DSM-5-C4Dataset Field values are controlled and managed via enterprise managed Reference and Master Data
			DSM-2-C5Dataset Descriptor includes reference to related Datasets and if applicable the relevant joining Dataset Fields	DSM-3-C5Value Level Metadata includes Resolvable Identifiers for Controlled and/or Standard Terms reported in the Dataset	DSM-4-C5The Semantic Data Model includes a pre-defined set of Common Data Elements reported within the Datasets and the relationships between them	DSM-5-C5Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language
			DSM-2-C6Dataset Descriptor includes Field-level Metadata as prescribed by a locally defined Dataset Model	DSM-3-C6Dataset Descriptor includes standard-compliant Field-level Metadata as prescribed by the adopted standard Dataset Model		
			DSM-2-C7Dataset Descriptor includes Value-level Metadata or if applicable includes a reference to a locally defined Data Dictionary	DSM-3-C7Dataset Descriptor references a standard license under which the dataset can be re-used.		
[H] Hosting environment capabilities	DSM-0-H1Data or metadata is hosted in non-accessible storage (e.g., personal desktop, local file system or archive)	DSM-1-H1Metadata hosting environment stores and maintains an identifiable Dataset Descriptor for each identifiable Dataset	DSM-2-H1The Data hosting environment's Persistence Model is aligned with a locally defined Domain Model to enable interpretation of Datasets	DSM-3-H1The Data hosting environment's Persistence Model is aligned with a standard Dataset model or compliant with relevant Minimum Information Reporting Guidelines	DSM-4-H1Data Hosting environment stores data in a relevant linked data store (e.g., Triple Store or Graph Database)	DSM-5-H1Hosting Environment implements Master Data Management Capability
	DSM-0-H2Data or metadata is hosted in an accessible resource but with no retrieval capability	DSM-1-H2The Dataset and its Descriptor are indexed and retrievable (in the same or separate hosting environments) via unique and persistent identifiers	DSM-2-H2Metadata hosting environment provides programmatic access and retrieval (API) for the Dataset Descriptor	DSM-3-H2For each dataset, the hosting environment maintains a globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifier for access and retrieval	DSM-4-H2Data Hosting Environment provides semantic querying capability	DSM-5-H2Hosting Environment implements Reference Data Management Capability
	DSM-0-H3Hosting environment does NOT offer searching capabilities to discover data or metadata	DSM-1-H3Retrieval of the Dataset and the Dataset Descriptor utilises a standardized communication protocol that is open, free and universally implementable	DSM-2-H3Data hosting environment offers the capability to browse and search related Datasets	DSM-3-H3Data Hosting environment utilises controlled terms and/or ontology terms to search within Dataset content.	DSM-4-H3Data Hosting Environment provides semantic search capability	DSM-5-H3Hosting Environment implements Data Governance Capability
		DSM-1-H4Metadata hosting environment offers the capability to browse and search contents of the Dataset Descriptor		DSM-3-H4If applicable, Dataset hosting environment offers dataset-level authentication and authorisation capabilities		

Figure 2. FAIR DSM Grid View. X-axis shows Maturity Levels, Y-axis shows the different categories of indicators.

The grid view allowed early model evaluators to see the trajectory of each group of indicators towards a path of increasing complexity and standardisation from lower to higher maturity levels. Also the grid view helped in grounding the idea that the state of FAIRness expressed at each maturity level can only be achieved by fulfilling the requirements across the three categories of indicators:

- Content-related,
- Representation & Format, and
- Hosting Environment Capabilities.

This highlighted more explicitly the often overlooked dependencies that exist amongst the FAIR principles, especially since many of those indicators are overlapping.

At first, no definitions or designations were given to the different levels of maturity, so the meaning of the levels developed as the group of indicators in each level converged towards a common **use** of data that collectively these indicators enabled and made possible.

The development of the model then went through three iterations of adding, removing and updating indicators that would both create a linked path across the different levels as well as a comprehensive set of requirements that delivered a

meaningful and a 'usable' state of FAIR data in each level across the three categories of FAIR requirements.

Figure 3. FAIR DSM categorization of FAIR requirements. First dimension is area of focus, second dimension is the level of data granularity in case of data requirements, or data management capability in case of hosting environment requirements.

Further refinements of the model then included the addition of a third dimension to further classify the model's indicators and their respective requirements. This dimension reflects the 'granularity' of the data that each subgroup of indicators focuses on. Figure 3 illustrates the addition of the granularity dimension, which provides better context and clarity to the focus of each group of indicators. Granularity of data & metadata was presented at the Study/Project level, Dataset level, Field level and data value level. Also with respect to the Hosting Environment Capabilities category, we further broke this down into three subgroups each focusing on enabling storage, retrieval or search capabilities.

The Assessment Scoring method

To assess the maturity of a given dataset, each FAIR DSM indicator is scored with a '1' or '0' to indicate whether or not the requirements specified by the indicator are satisfied. Then, a percentage of the indicators that are considered to be satisfied is calculated to provide an indication of percent completion towards compliance with each of the maturity levels.

As illustrated by Figure 4, the final score for each maturity level is expressed as a percentage of completion towards satisfying each level's requirements in each of the three areas of focus: 'Content and context', 'Representation and format' and 'Hosting environment capabilities'. Also, a 'Total' percentage of all indicators that were satisfied for each level is provided. This method was also embedded into the FAIR-DSM Assessment tool⁷.

Figure 4 also shows the assessment scores Pre-FAIRification and Post-FAIRification, which highlights the area of improvements after the FAIRification process has been implemented. The example in Figure 4 shows that the dataset was at 45% towards completing Level 1 before FAIRification, but reached 100% Level 1 after FAIRification and also achieved higher Percentage completion towards categories of Level 2.

		Pre-FAIRification Status	Post FAIRification Status
		% Completed	% Completed
Level 0	Content ant context	0	0
	Representation and format	0	0
	Hosting environment capabilities	0	0
	Total	0	0
Level 1	Content ant context	50	100
	Representation and format	33.33333333	100
	Hosting environment capabilities	50	100
	Total	45	100
Level 2	Content ant context	83	100
	Representation and format	100	100
	Hosting environment capabilities	0	33
	Total	69	85
Level 3	Content ant context	0	29
	Representation and format	25	25
	Hosting environment capabilities	0	0
	Total	7	21
Level 4	Content ant context	0	0
	Representation and format	0	100
	Hosting environment capabilities	0	0
	Total	0	17
Level 5	Content ant context	0	0
	Representation and format		
	Hosting environment capabilities		
	Total	0	0

Figure 4. Example of FAIR DSM scoring

⁷ <https://github.com/FAIRplus/FAIR-DSM-Assessment-Tool>

3. Results

The FAIR DSM model

Conceptual Model

Figure 5 illustrates the conceptual model underlying the FAIR DSM model. A **Dataset** is the unit of Data that is defined for the purpose of sharing and reuse. This means that as a prerequisite to adopting the FAIR-DSM model, adopters should consider the form and the representation of their data as Datasets that are designed and purposed for sharing and re-use by users unfamiliar with the data. The model also refers to the unit of metadata that describes each Dataset as the **Dataset Descriptor**. This ‘objectification’ of data and metadata helps reduce the ambiguity often associated with these terms. Datasets are also contextualised by being associated with a **Domain Model**, which provides the necessary information to understand and interpret the dataset(s) content and any relationships that may exist between the contents of multiple datasets within a study or project. Finally, both Datasets and their Descriptors are expected to be deposited in **hosting environments** that offer a set of capabilities that enable and support the expected use of the FAIRified Datasets.

Figure 5. FAIR DSM Conceptual Model

The FAIR DSM Indicators

The nuts and bolts of the FAIR DSM model are the list of 73 indicators classified by three dimensions as described in the Methods section:

1) the Level of Maturity, 2) the Area of Focus (content & context, representation & format or hosting capabilities) and 3) the 'Data Granularity Level' (dataset, field, value) or the 'Capability' in case of hosting-related indicators. Figure 5 also illustrates how these indicators are organised according to the component they provide guidance/assessment for.

Maturity Model: Levels

5	Managed Data Assets	Enterprise Level. Data at this level is optimally managed at the most granular level in an environment offering data governance, master data management and reference data management capabilities.
4	Semantically Typed Data	Cross-community Level. This level focuses on cross-domain interoperability and is meant to be the level required for larger harmonization and integration projects.
3	Standardised Data	Community Level. Data at this level complies with community standard domain models, terminologies and formats, and is hosted in an environment offering searching and retrieval capabilities.
2	Described Data	Project Level. All datasets generated within a project are consistently described against a locally defined schema, controlled terminologies, and hosted in an environment offering data catalogue level searching capabilities.
1	Identifiable Data	Data Object level. Data at this level is identifiable as individual generic data objects and described by generic metadata elements. Hosting environment offers limited retrieval capabilities.
0	Single Use Data	No potential for re-use beyond lifetime of the research project

Figure 6. FAIR DSM Levels of Maturity.

The FAIR DSM model presents five levels of maturity, which represent the state of FAIRness optimised for a data usage goal. Each level is characterised by increasing requirements across the three categories of the FAIR DSM model: content-related, representation and format and hosting environment capabilities. The first objective of the model was achieved by requiring each level to satisfy a set of requirements from each category of indicators to make sure that a state-of-FAIRness is achieved with a target data usability goal. Therefore, each level of maturity is established by a set of indicators that cover each and every component of the FAIR DSM conceptual model as illustrated in Figure 1.

A convention for indicator identification was developed to reflect this classification. DSM-[x]-[C|R|H][d], where 'x' denotes the level of maturity this indicator belongs to. 'C' denotes that the indicator belongs to the 'Content and Context' focused class of indicators, 'R' denotes that the indicator belongs to the 'Representation and Format' class, and 'H' denotes that the indicator belongs to the 'Hosting Environment Capabilities' class of indicators. Finally, 'd' is a number that denotes the component to which the indicator provides guidance/assessment for its status in a given maturity level. For example, DSM-[x]-R2 are a group of indicators that prescribe different requirements for *how the Datasets are represented in each level of maturity* where 'x'

denotes the level of maturity. Table below lists indicators for the 'Dataset Model' indicators (R2) for each level of maturity.

INDICATORID	INDICATOR
DSM-0-R2	No representation of Data purposed for sharing and re-use is available
DSM-1-R2	Data intended for sharing and reuse have a purposely defined representation as Datasets
DSM-2-R2	Dataset(s) are standardised to a locally defined Dataset Model suitable for data sharing and re-use
DSM-3-R2	Dataset(s) are standardised to relevant Domain or Community Standard Dataset Model(s) suitable for data sharing and re-use
DSM-4-R2	Dataset(s) are standardised to a defined Semantic Data Model and represented using Linked Data Representations suitable for data sharing and re-use
DSM-5-R2	Dataset(s) intended for sharing and re-use are granularly standardised and managed at the Data Element Level (e.g. ISO 11179 MDR standard)

FAIR-DSM Level 0

Level 0 is a reference level representing a state of data that is missing one or more fundamental FAIR requirements. Data at this level has diminished potential for reuse as it does not meet the minimum set of requirements to be findable or accessible beyond the lifetime of its original research project.

ID	Indicator Description
DSM-0-C0	<u>Dataset(s)</u> are NOT Identifiable via Unique Identifiers
DSM-0-C1	Metadata does NOT contain context-related information required to interpret the data
DSM-0-C2	<u>Dataset Descriptor</u> does NOT include a reference to the Dataset it describes
DSM-0-R1	Contextual Metadata is NOT formally represented in any form
DSM-0-R2	No representation of Data purposed for <u>sharing</u> and re-use is available
DSM-0-R3	Metadata is available but NOT formally represented in a structured <u>Dataset Descriptor</u>
DSM-0-R4	Metadata is NOT available in a <u>Machine Readable Format</u>
DSM-0-R5	<u>Dataset(s)</u> are NOT available in a <u>Machine Readable Format</u>
DSM-0-H1	Data or metadata is hosted in NON-accessible storage (e.g., personal desktop, local file system or archive)
DSM-0-H2	Data or metadata is hosted in an accessible resource but with NO retrieval capability
DSM-0-H3	Hosting environment does NOT offer searching capabilities to discover data or metadata

FAIR-DSM Level 1

In level 1, data is identifiable as individual generic data objects that are described by generic metadata elements. Hosting environment offers limited searching & retrieval capabilities. This level prescribes the entry level requirements that all the higher levels

will build up upon. It establishes basic requirements to enable ‘Findability’, ‘Accessibility’ with basic descriptive metadata that enables data users to interpret and understand the data object. The first step to be at Maturity Level 1 is to define and identify the data object that is expected to be shared and re-used (i.e., the FAIR Dataset).

ID	Indicator Description
DSM-1-C0	Each <u>Dataset</u> purposed for <u>sharing and re-use</u> is assigned a unique identifier
DSM-1-C1	<u>Dataset Descriptor(s)</u> includes Descriptive Study/Project-Level summary information
DSM-1-C2	<u>Dataset Descriptor(s)</u> includes Identifying & Descriptive Dataset-Level metadata
DSM-1-C3	<u>Dataset Descriptor(s)</u> contains access information for the <u>Dataset</u>
DSM-1-R0	Dataset Metadata is formally represented in the form of an Identifiable <u>Dataset Descriptor</u>
DSM-1-R1	<u>Contextual Metadata</u> is represented at summary level and reported in the <u>Dataset Descriptor</u>
DSM-1-R2	Data intended for sharing and reuse have a purposely defined representation as Datasets
DSM-1-R3	A representation of the <u>Dataset Descriptor</u> conforming to a relevant <u>General Purpose Metadata Schema</u> is available
DSM-1-R4	<u>Dataset Descriptor</u> is available in <u>Machine Readable Format</u>
DSM-1-R5	<u>Dataset(s)</u> available in <u>Machine Readable Format</u>
DSM-1-H1	Metadata hosting environment stores and maintains an identifiable <u>Dataset Descriptor</u> for each identifiable <u>Dataset</u>
DSM-1-H2	The <u>Dataset</u> and its <u>Descriptor</u> are indexed and retrievable (in the same or separate hosting environments) via unique and persistent identifiers
DSM-1-H3	Retrieval of the <u>Dataset</u> and the <u>Dataset Descriptor</u> utilises a standardised communication protocol that is open, free and universally implementable
DSM-1-H4	Metadata hosting environment offers the capability to browse and search contents of the <u>Dataset Descriptor</u>

FAIR-DSM Level 2

Level 2 aims to enhance the usability of a project, or a study's structured data, which often are represented by multiple related datasets. Different projects usually have their own data model and collect different subsets of clinical, molecular, imaging or other data. The FAIRplus-DSM model distinguishes between structured data, unstructured data, and data objects in a project. Structured data include subject-based clinical data, sample-based assay data and other data associated with the data schema. Therefore, indicators at this level, refer to the FAIR Data Object as the Dataset indicating more requirements related to the *structural metadata of the Dataset* are defined, namely the ‘Dataset Fields’ and the corresponding ‘Dataset Field Values’.

This level of maturity aims to increase the FAIRness level of structured data by focusing on Dataset-level structural metadata and Project-level contextual metadata. This level

of maturity is also aimed at data hosted within project-based data repositories, general purpose data repositories or data catalogues. In terms of hosting, level 2 compliant datasets would be hosted in project-specific or institutional data repositories that provide all the accessibility and storage capabilities required for sharing and reusing data within project data users.

ID	Indicator Description
DSM-2-C1	The locally defined <u>Domain Model</u> contains concepts that describe the overall project/study design, the relationships between the Datasets, the key entities reported within the Datasets and the relationships between them.
DSM-2-C2	Where applicable, data is structured in the Dataset according to the <u>Tidy Data Principles</u>
DSM-2-C3	Dataset(s) include <u>Reference Fields</u> that enable joining related datasets
DSM-2-C4	Where applicable, Dataset Field Values are standardised against a locally defined <u>Data Dictionary</u> within and across related Datasets
DSM-2-C5	<u>Dataset Descriptor</u> includes reference to related <u>Datasets</u> and if applicable the relevant joining <u>Dataset Fields</u>
DSM-2-C6	<u>Dataset Descriptor</u> includes <u>Field-level Metadata</u> as prescribed by a locally defined <u>Dataset Model</u>
DSM-2-C7	<u>Dataset Descriptor</u> includes <u>Value-level Metadata</u> or if applicable includes a reference to a locally defined <u>Data Dictionary</u>
DSM-2-R1	<u>Contextual Metadata</u> is formally represented and reported in the form of a locally defined <u>Domain Model</u>
DSM-2-R2	Dataset(s) are standardised to a locally defined Dataset Model suitable for data sharing and re-use
DSM-2-R3	<u>Dataset Descriptor(s)</u> adopt a Metadata Schema representation that describes the locally defined Dataset Model including its structural metadata (i.e. Field-level and Value-level metadata)
DSM-2-R4	A formal documentation of the <u>locally defined Domain Model</u> is available in a Human Readable Format
DSM-2-R5	<u>Dataset(s)</u> available in <u>Machine Readable Format</u>
DSM-2-H1	The Data hosting environment's Persistence Model is aligned with a locally defined <u>Domain Model</u> to enable interpretation of Datasets
DSM-2-H2	Metadata hosting environment provides programmatic access and retrieval (API) for the <u>Dataset Descriptor</u>
DSM-2-H3	Data hosting environment offers the capability to browse and search related Datasets

FAIR-DSM Level 3

This level of maturity is defined at the community level. The data at this level complies with community standard domain models, terminologies and formats, and is hosted in data resources offering advanced searching and API-based retrieval capabilities for community-wide data discovery and re-use enablement.

ID	Indicator Description
DSM-3-C1	Where applicable, study-level / experimental metadata is reported in compliance with relevant Minimum Information <u>Reporting Guidelines</u>

DSM-3-C2	Where applicable, Dataset(s) definition and content are reported in compliance with relevant community-defined Data Reporting Guidelines
DSM-3-C3	Where applicable, Dataset Field Names use standard controlled terms as recommended by the adopted Standard
DSM-3-C4	Where applicable, Dataset Field Values are standardised against domain-specific <u>Controlled Terminologies</u> and/or <u>Ontology Terms</u>
DSM-3-C5	Value Level Metadata includes Resolvable Identifiers for Controlled and/or Standard Terms reported in the Dataset
DSM-3-C6	Dataset Descriptor includes standard-compliant Field-level Metadata as prescribed by the adopted standard Dataset Model.
DSM-3-C7	Dataset Descriptor references a standard licence under which the dataset can be reused.
DSM-3-R1	<u>Contextual Metadata</u> is formally represented and modelled according to a community or domain-specific standard
DSM-3-R2	Dataset(s) are standardised to relevant Domain or Community Standard Dataset Model(s) suitable for data sharing and re-use
DSM-3-R3	<u>Dataset Descriptor(s)</u> use community-defined or domain-specific metadata standard
DSM-3-R4	A formal documentation of the adopted Standard Dataset Model is available in a <u>Machine Readable Format</u>
DSM-3-R5	<u>Dataset(s)</u> available in non-proprietary <u>Machine Readable Format</u> as prescribed by a standard <u>Dataset Model</u>
DSM-3-H1	The Data hosting environment's Persistence Model is aligned with a standard <u>Dataset model</u> or compliant with relevant <u>Minimum Information Reporting Guidelines</u>
DSM-3-H2	For each dataset, the hosting environment maintains a globally unique, persistent and resolvable identifier for access and retrieval
DSM-3-H3	Data Hosting environment utilises controlled terms and/or ontology terms to search within Dataset content.
DSM-3-H4	If applicable, Dataset hosting environment offers dataset-level authentication and authorisation capabilities

FAIR-DSM Level 4

This level of maturity is defined at the cross-community level. At this level, the focus is on cross-domain interoperability and is meant to be the level required for big-science projects requiring data harmonisation and multi-modal data integration. Level 4 is an aspirational level of FAIR maturity. The main focus of Level 4 is establishing semantic interoperability between datasets within and across multiple studies.

ID	Indicator Description
DSM-4-C1	A Semantic Data Model includes study design <u>Data Elements</u> and the relationships between them
DSM-4-C2	Dataset(s) content is harmonised against a designed-for-purpose <u>Semantic Data Model</u>
DSM-4-C3	Key Dataset Fields are mapped to <u>Common Data Elements</u> as defined by the <u>Semantic Data Model</u>

DSM-4-C4	Values for key Domain Entities reported in the Dataset(s) are standardised and assigned unique Standard Identifiers
DSM-4-C5	The Semantic Data Model includes a predefined set of Common Data Elements reported within the Datasets and the relationships between them
DSM-4-R1	Contextual Metadata is formally represented by a set of semantically defined <u>Common Data Elements</u>
DSM-4-R2	Dataset(s) are standardised to a defined Semantic Data Model and represented using Linked Data Representations suitable for data sharing and re-use
DSM-4-R3	A <u>Semantic Data Model</u> (Metadata) used for data harmonisation across Datasets is formally defined and represented using Linked Data Representations
DSM-4-R4	A Semantic Data Model (Metadata) describing the data is represented in a Machine Readable and Machine Interpretable format
DSM-4-R5	Datasets are available in a Machine Readable and Machine Interpretable format
DSM-4-R6	If applicable, licence information and/or permitted use and accessibility to parts of the dataset is formally represented and encoded in a Machine Readable Format
DSM-4-H1	Data Hosting environment stores data in a relevant linked data store (e.g., Triple Store or Graph Database)
DSM-4-H2	Data Hosting Environment provides semantic querying capability
DSM-4-H3	Data Hosting Environment provides semantic search capability

FAIR-DSM Level 5

This level of maturity is defined at the enterprise level. Data at level 5 is optimally *managed* at the most granular level in an environment offering data governance, master data and reference data management capabilities. Indicators for this level are still under development as use cases were limited to test and validate this FAIR enabled data use case, which would be more relevant to big data-science driven enterprises.

ID	Indicator Description
DSM-5-C1	WHAT's included in the MASTER Data Consolidation Model
DSM-5-C2	What is included in the MASTER Dataset Model
DSM-5-C3	Dataset Fields are linked and harmonised against enterprise managed Metadata Elements (e.g. MDR registered Data Elements)
DSM-5-C4	Dataset Field values are controlled and managed via enterprise managed Reference and Master Data
DSM-5-C5	Metadata includes provenance information according to a cross-community language
DSM-5-R1	Data content and context is defined and managed by Master Data Management
DSM-5-R2	Dataset(s) intended for sharing and re-use are granularly standardised and managed at the Data Element Level (e.g. ISO 11179 MDR standard)
DSM-5-R3	Common Data Elements and their value sets are defined and registered in a managed Metadata Registry
DSM-5-R4	<i>[Metadata Formatting requirements]</i>
DSM-5-R5	<i>[Dataset Formatting requirements]</i>
DSM-5-H1	Hosting Environment implements Master Data Management Capability

DSM-5-H2	Hosting Environment implements Reference Data Management Capability
DSM-5-H3	Hosting Environment implements Data Governance Capability

The FAIR DSM Assessment Tool

The FAIR DSM Assessment tool⁸ is an easy-to-use web application allowing data owners across the globe to assess the maturity of their datasets. Using the web interface, users are guided through the DSM model in a questionnaire format, answering and selecting indicators to which their dataset complies. As indicated by Figure 7, the interface has 3 ‘tabs’ based on the 3 areas of focus of the model: Representation, Content and Context, and Hosting. Each of these three tabs must be completed in order to progress through the tool. To facilitate ease of access, the tool performs smart decisions allowing users to skip questions which are not applicable to their dataset based on prior answers. The tool exposes compliance levels at each question, backfilling lower level compliance to lesser maturity levels.

FAIR DataSet Maturity (FAIR-DSM) Assessment Tool

Figure 7. Overview of the questionnaire window of the FAIR-DSM

To assist non-expert users, the tool is backed by an extensive glossary (<https://fairplus.github.io/Data-Maturity/docs/Glossary/>), as well as providing guidance and examples, through an expandable ‘click’ box at the top of each question page (Figure 8).

⁸ <https://fairdsm.biospeak.solutions/>

Representation & Format | Content & Context | Hosting Environment Capabilities

Focus: Dataset Representation

More Info

This is a pre-requisite requirement to define the unit of data that is the subject-matter of the FAIRification process. This requirement requires the data managers to consider the form and the representation of data into Datasets that are designed and purposed for sharing and re-use by users unfamiliar with the data.

[1 of 17] Which of the following statements best describes the current state of Data to be shared and re-used?

Figure 8. A questionnaire assisted with a drop-down example to understand the question context.

Upon completion of the questionnaire, which is determined by clicking the ‘submit’ button on the application, the results are presented in the browser window, and are available to download. The results represent the percentage completion of each of the FAIR Maturity levels with respect to the 3 areas of focus.

4. Discussion

Integration with the FAIRplus FAIRification Process

The FAIR DSM tool is designed to be added to existing FAIRification pipelines. A successful application of the tool can be observed in the FAIRplus FAIRification framework (<https://zenodo.org/record/7157066#.Y2PYu3bMJaQ>, <https://w3id.org/faircookbook/FCB079>). The framework is distributed into three major components: the FAIRification Process, the FAIRification Template, and FAIRification Workplan. The FAIRification process lays the basic foundation for decision-driven FAIRification strategies (propagated and reflected through the FAIRification Template and Workflows). The FAIR DSM is part of this decision with the aim of providing feedback on the implementation. Prior to beginning of the FAIRification strategy, the FAIR DSM assessment is performed to get an idea on the FAIR status of the data and identification of improvement factors within each dataset (content, hosting, and/or representation). On the basis of the assessment, a set of implementation strategies can be identified to enhance the FAIRification status of the dataset. At regular intervals, the FAIR DSM assessment is performed for better alignment with the FAIRification goals for the dataset. The imSAVAR project was involved in such an assessment. The

initial assessment result suggested that the dataset undergoing FAIRification did not yet meet the criteria for Level 1 maturity. The assessment report allowed us to identify key steps of the FAIRification work plan needed to reach Level 2. The FAIRification steps needed included the generation of a common data dictionary for all parts of the dataset and the standardisation of common variables such as cell types, species and tissue sources against public domain ontologies. Due to factors outside the FAIRification team's control, such as lack of input over the dataset's proprietary commercial hosting platform, some tasks related to content and hosting could not be included in the work plan. Overall however, the FAIRification tasks related to representation and format of the data and metadata led to a post-FAIRification score of almost Level 3 for this domain.

In addition to the top-to-bottom (prospective) approach of FAIR DSM assessment, a retrospective fitting of the FAIRification goals with the assessment can also be performed. In this bottom-to-top approach, a set of FAIR levels and goals are predefined and the FAIR DSM model is used to assess the tasks required for reaching that level and identification of the level reached upon completion of the goal respectively. The GNA-NOW project was involved in such an assessment. Prior to the assessment, the improvement of the metadata capture template through the use of standardised terminologies had been identified as the primary area of work. The DSM assessment highlighted that the pre-FAIRification dataset failed to even meet all indicators for Level 1 in the area of Representation & Format, and had maturity gaps in all areas at Level 2 (Figure 9). Prior to the assessment, the initial plan had the intention of carrying out tasks that belonged to higher maturity levels (Levels 3 and 4). However, after using the FAIR-DSM model assessment, unforeseen gaps were identified as higher priorities, which allowed the refinement of the work plan to include targeted steps for closing maturity gaps at Level 1 and 2, such as defining formal dataset descriptors and including study- and project-level metadata. Although Level 3 maturity could ultimately not be achieved due to gaps related to Content and Hosting requirements that were outside the team's control, all requirements for Level 1 and 2 were met across all three areas of the DSM, while Representation & Format requirements were met in full up to Level 3.

FAIR DataSet Maturity (FAIR-DSM) Assessment Tool

Level	Representation & Format	Content & Context	Hosting Environment Capabilities	Overall Level % Completion
Level 1	67%	100%	100%	86%
Level 2	50%	78%	75%	67%
Level 3	13%	0%	60%	20%
Level 4	0%	0%	0%	0%
Level 5	0%	0%	0%	0%

Figure 9. Summary report card for pre-assessment performed for IMI GNA-NOW

Overall, the integration of the FAIR DSM assessment into the FAIRification process represents a crucial element in the overall success of the FAIRification process. Not only is the DSM essential to guide and refine the initial work plan development, it also serves to regularly review the progress of the plan implementation to ensure that available FAIRification resources are deployed with maximal efficiency to reach the intended goal. Following the completion of FAIRification efforts, the differences in pre- and post-FAIRification maturity serve as a simple and clear illustration of the success of the work.

Pre- and post-FAIRification maturity levels for all datasets processed through the FAIRplus FAIRification framework are published in the Translational Data Catalog⁹. A collection of all assessments¹⁰ is in preparation and will be published on Zenodo in due course.

Integration with the FAIR Cookbook

Where applicable, the recipes in the FAIR Cookbook were annotated with one or more FAIR-DSM indicators, implying which maturity level(s) and area(s) of focus of the model (content, representation or hosting) may be fulfilled by implementing the entire recipe. The correct annotation of the recipes with the relevant indicators was assessed by both the author(s) of each recipe and the FAIR-DSM team. Not all the recipes could be annotated with an indicator. Similarly, for some indicators, dominantly those in levels 4

⁹https://datacatalog.elixir-luxembourg.org/datasets?query=&sort_by=dataset_title&order=asc&fair_evaluation=FAIRplus%20Evaluation

¹⁰<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1G-8h6Ao7GzUyoqFB7ClkB-ql6q0UYQOhFYhzFEval6k/edit#gid=102053453>

and 5, there was no recipe, which highlights the gaps in the FAIR cookbook and provides guidance on the creation of new content and recipes.

5. Conclusion

In this report we have outlined the development of the FAIR-DSM model, which we believe to be the first maturity model for state-of-FAIRness improvement for research datasets. The FAIR Dataset Maturity model is a hands-on reference model that provides guidance for FAIR implementations in life science research projects. The model was developed and verified in collaboration with 20 IMI projects that FAIRplus engaged with. The model is intended for open use and will continue to be maintained on github¹¹ hoping to build a community around it to further its development and deployment on a wide scale.

¹¹ <https://github.com/FAIRplus/Data-Maturity>